

Theory of Anything

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(Time is a series of separate frames that are connected. The distance between frames is zero, and you nimbly jump to the next one. Time is a great illusion that is easy to distinguish from the truth. It is a whole line of which you are a part, seeing only the part that is directly behind you as you move further through the universe. Everything is already in place in the universe — you can check it by running through it or glancing at it. Your legs get tired, and your eyes don't rotate in a circle, so you can't see everything. They are held back by a myriad of existential questions about what is out there, far away, where we are not. You need to get heroic and stop thinking of yourself as the center of the universe, but be sure to leave yourself on the periphery.)

The past can be felt, which means it is in the present. Movement too, which means it is already in place as well.

Illogicality changes the composition of things, but does not destroy them, nor does it destroy what holds them together — the universe. You may not feel logic if it does not appear. Logic and causality can be misleading. Logic is not the correct relationship between two things, but their specific identical quality. If you imagine all possible qualities, it is as rare as the rest. The universe is not a container, but a common quality, or a combination of qualities, of all its things. They are found in every thing in the universe, and you don't need to name, compare, or analyze them to feel it, but it can happen in parallel. A purely strange thing can only be found next to other strange things. You are a thing, just like the rest, and you are felt because you exist. You are all together because you are similar.

There are no clues to suggest that there are worlds other than mine, but here I can fantasize and assume their existence. For the sake of clarity, one can imagine that there are an infinite number of unique qualities. They can be numbered from 1 to infinity and grouped in a unique

way. The rearrangement of qualities in combinations does not matter, because the world is not just mathematics with its elements and tricks, whether already discovered or not. Permutation is not part of my idea. Thus, things can be represented as having either a single unique quality or a unique combination of qualities. They can be very similar or completely different, but they never repeat themselves. Their permutation also does not change anything.

Now we need to find a way to sort them into different universes. This needs to be done because my world clearly does not contain all possible things. Thing [1,2] cannot be with thing [3,4] because they lack at least one common quality. Thing [1,2,3,4] could go to different universes, but according to the uniqueness rule, this is not allowed. This rule is not just for aesthetics. I hope that by following it, one can find an unambiguous place for all things. For example, a universe with things [1], [1,2], [1,2,3], [1,2,3,4], [1,2,3,4,5] is a terrible way to pack them. If you try to find other universes using it, performing operations on it, you will inevitably encounter repetitions of things. By operation, I mean throwing a layer of identical numbers on it, for example, {5,5,5,5,5}. If an item has a quality of 5, it is crossed out, and if not, it is added. In addition, there cannot be more than one universe with the same overall quality, or a combination of them. From a correctly constructed universe, you can find all the others.

The disappearance of things when you turn away from them, the disappearance of a friend with whom you only correspond — these things are not surprising, but that does not mean you should turn a blind eye to them. Nothing happens beyond your perception. A change in the direction of your gaze and, with it, a change in the picture. A change in the picture from your thoughts, a change in the picture after sleep, from your deep concentration, inattention, focus of vision, stupidity, and genius. The thing did not change while you were away; it did not intersect with you in any way. Everything works in some kind of disjointed jumps. You can't look at the "same" thing twice in exactly the same way, and that makes it different. An N-thing, an N-thing is red, an N-thing is boring. An N-thing is whatever you want it to be. In "one" thing, qualities and their combinations meet and diverge. At some point, the small changes will be exhausted and bigger ones will come. The n-th thing (combination of qualities) will be overwhelmed by other qualities, but you will not stop feeling it, even though you will see something that is barely comparable to the original version. A cloud with the outline of a dog and just a cloud. There is no particular priority for any qualities; the perception of a thing depends on its entire composition. Many things that are red, that are Suns, that are people. Many of the same particles with spin up or down on shimmering screens, behind gleaming glasses and bright eyes.

Strong trust in exact science. A blind old woman, hunched over, rummages through things with her rough hands, grabs only some of them, tears pieces off them, and crumples them up.

It seems as if she knows exactly what she is looking for. She devours them, and you notice that among the useless things there is something truly important and new, but it is just her dry fingernail. She knows exactly who to kill and who to leave alive. She healed people with dark and light hair, with and without eyes, pig organs, in coffins and rigged articles, different people. Different people in photographs, stories, memories, in the past, she destroyed them too. Humanity, unborn mice, dead mice, mice with human ears.

Your drawn-out, yet such a brief existence is a sign that there was at least one version of you before you stopped recognizing yourself.